

ASSESSMENT OF THE CURRENT STATUS OF KINDERGARTEN PROGRAM IN SELECTED PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS OF SIATON DISTRICT I

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20022896>

ABSTRACT

This study assessed the current status of Kindergarten programs in selected public elementary schools in Siaton District I and identified areas needing improvement. Specifically, it examined the profile of respondents, teachers' level of competence, stakeholders' perceptions regarding program implementation, and challenges encountered in delivery. The study employed a quantitative descriptive research design using a researcher-made survey questionnaire administered to teachers, school heads/principals, and parents through purposive sampling. Data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and nonparametric statistical tools such as Spearman rho correlation and Kruskal–Wallis H test due to the non-normal distribution of data. Open-ended responses were treated using thematic analysis. Findings revealed that teachers demonstrated a high level of competence in implementing the Kindergarten program, particularly in instructional strategies, assessment practices, and stakeholder engagement. Significant relationships were found between teachers' competence and selected profile variables such as age, years of service, and educational attainment, while sex and area of specialization showed no significant relationship. Results further showed no significant difference in the perceptions of teachers, school heads/principals, and parents regarding program implementation, indicating shared views among stakeholders. However, challenges such as limited resources, inconsistent facilities, and the need for continuous professional development were identified. The study concluded that Kindergarten programs in Siaton District I were generally well implemented, but sustained support, resource enhancement, and professional growth opportunities were necessary to ensure consistent and high-quality delivery across schools.

Keywords: *Kindergarten Program, Teacher Competence, Program Implementation, Stakeholder Perceptions, Kindergarten Education*

INTRODUCTION

Early Childhood Education (ECE) is globally recognized as a critical foundation for lifelong learning and development. International organizations such as UNESCO (2022) and UNICEF (2024) emphasize that quality ECE promotes children's cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development, particularly during the formative years from birth to age eight. Early childhood is widely acknowledged as a crucial period of rapid brain development, where appropriate learning experiences significantly influence a child's future well-being and learning outcomes. Recent global reports further indicate that participation in quality early learning programs enhances school readiness, supports language and cognitive development, and improves social competence among young learners (UNICEF, 2024; UNESCO, 2022). Consequently, many countries prioritize investments in ECE, focusing on developmentally appropriate curricula, qualified teachers, child-friendly learning environments, and strong family and community engagement. Global trends in ECE also highlight the importance of quality assurance, inclusive practices, and continuous monitoring of program implementation to ensure positive learning outcomes.

In the Philippine context, the government has institutionalized Kindergarten Education through legal and policy frameworks. Republic Act No. 10157 mandates compulsory and universal kindergarten education for all five-year-old children, serving as the primary legal basis for the provision of kindergarten in public elementary schools. The Department of Education (DepEd), through policies such as DepEd Order No. 47 s. 2016, provides guidelines on the implementation of the Kindergarten Program, emphasizing age-appropriate learning standards, child-centered teaching approaches, adequate facilities, learning materials, and active parental involvement. While these policies ensure nationwide access to Kindergarten Education, recent reports continue to indicate variations in the quality of program implementation, particularly in terms of available resources, administrative support, and monitoring mechanisms across public schools (UNICEF Philippines, 2020).

At the local level, public elementary schools in Siaton District I offer kindergarten classes as mandated by Republic Act No. 10157. Observations within the district reveal differences in the availability of physical facilities, learning materials, parental involvement, and administrative practices, which may affect the effectiveness and sustainability of Kindergarten program. Although schools comply with the requirement to provide kindergarten education, the quality of implementation may vary due to contextual factors such as school resources, leadership support, and community participation.

Despite the established provision of Kindergarten Program in Siaton District I, there remained a research gap in systematically assessing the current status of these program. Existing studies primarily focus on program compliance and access, with limited examination of the strengths, challenges, and gaps in key implementation areas such as physical facilities, learning materials, curricular and co-curricular activities, and positive school practices. Furthermore, there is insufficient local evidence that consolidates the perspectives of school heads/principals, teachers, and parents in evaluating how

Kindergarten program is carried out at the school level. Addressing this gap is essential to understanding whether current practices adequately support developmentally appropriate learning experiences for kindergarten learners.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the current status of Kindergarten programs in selected public elementary schools in Siaton District I and determine areas for improvement. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - Teachers*
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 educational attainment;
 - 1.4 area of specialization;
 - 1.5 years of service in Kindergarten; and
 - 1.6 relevant seminars and trainings attended in the last five years?
 - School Heads/Principals*
 - 1.7 sex;
 - 1.8 number of years as school head/principal;
 - 1.9 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.10 area of specialization;
 - 1.11 innovations initiated; and
 - 1.12 seminars, trainings, or workshops facilitated or coordinated?
 - Parents*
 - 1.13 age;
 - 1.14 sex;
 - 1.15 educational attainment; and
 - 1.16 occupation?
2. To what extent do *teachers* demonstrate competence in implementing the Kindergarten program in terms of:
 - 2.1 knowledge and application of instructional strategies;
 - 2.2 use of assessment methods to monitor learning outcomes;
 - 2.3 integration of curricular and co-curricular activities;
 - 2.4 utilization of physical facilities and learning materials; and
 - 2.5 engagement with parents and other stakeholders to support learning?
3. To what extent do the respondents perceive the implementation of the Kindergarten program in relation to:
 - Availability and adequacy of physical facilities*
 - 3.1 As perceived by teachers
 - 3.2 As perceived by school heads/principals
 - 3.3 As perceived by parents

Availability and adequacy of learning materials

3.4 As perceived by teachers

3.5 As perceived by school heads/principals

3.6 As perceived by parents

Implementation of curricular and co-curricular activities

3.7 As perceived by teachers

3.8 As perceived by school heads/principals

3.9 As perceived by parents

Use of instructional strategies and assessment methods

3.10 As perceived by teachers

3.11 As perceived by school heads/principals

3.12 As perceived by parents

Stakeholder support (parents, community, and school administrators)

3.13 As perceived by teachers

3.14 As perceived by school heads/principals

4. Is there significant relationships between the profile of teacher respondents and their level of competence in implementing the Kindergarten program?
5. Is there a significant difference in the perceptions of teachers, school heads/principals, and parents regarding the implementation of the Kindergarten program?
6. What challenges or gaps are encountered in the implementation of the Kindergarten program?
7. Based on the findings of the study, what areas for improvement may be proposed to enhance the implementation of the Kindergarten program?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative descriptive research design to assess the current status of the Kindergarten Program in selected public elementary schools in Siaton District I. The locale included schools situated in both accessible and remote communities to capture varied conditions of program delivery. The respondents were composed of kindergarten teachers, school heads/principals, and parents of kindergarten learners. Purposive sampling was used to select participants who were directly involved in the implementation of the program.

The study utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire as the primary instrument for data gathering. Three sets of questionnaires were prepared for teachers, school heads/principals, and parents. The instrument consisted of three parts: (1) profile of respondents, (2) assessment of Program Implementation, and (3) open-ended questions on challenges and suggested improvements. The areas covered included physical facilities, learning materials, instructional practices, curricular and co-curricular activities, and stakeholder support. A 4-point Likert scale was used: 4 = Excellent, 3 = Best, 2 = Good, and 1 = Poor. The questionnaire underwent expert validation, pilot testing, and reliability testing, which showed high internal consistency.

Prior to the conduct of the study, permission was secured from the proper educational authorities. After approval, the questionnaires were distributed to the selected respondents and retrieved upon completion. Guidance was provided to respondents, particularly parents, to ensure clear understanding of the items.

Data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and nonparametric statistical tools due to the non-normal distribution of data. Spearman rho correlation was used to determine relationships involving Teacher Competence, while the Kruskal–Wallis H test was used to test differences in Stakeholder Perceptions. Open-ended responses were analyzed through simple content analysis.

The study was limited to selected public elementary schools in Siaton District I and focused only on the present implementation of the Kindergarten Program. Private schools, daycare centers, and long-term learner outcomes in Kindergarten Education were not included.

RESULTS

Profile for Teachers

Table 1.1
Age Distribution of Teachers

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percent
30-35	6	50.00
36-40	1	8.33
41-45	3	25.00
46-50	1	8.33
51 and above	1	8.33
Total	12	100.00

Table 1.2
Sex Distribution of Teachers

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Female	12	100.00
Total	12	100.00

Table 1.3
Highest Educational Attainment of Teachers

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Bachelor's Degree	10	83.33
Master's Degree Holder	1	8.33
Masters- 30 UNITS	1	8.33
Total	12	100.0

Table 1.4
Teacher's Area of Specialization

Specialization	Frequency	Percent
Social Studies	1	8.33
Social Studies/Early Childhood Education	1	8.33
General Curriculum/Administration	1	8.33
Filipino	2	16.67
Early Childhood Education	2	16.67
General Curriculum	5	41.67
Total	12	100.00

Table 1.5
Number of Years as Teachers in Kindergarten

Years	Frequency	Percent
1	1	8.33
2	1	8.33
3	2	16.67
4	1	8.33
5	1	8.33
8	1	8.33
10	2	8.33
11	1	8.33
12	1	8.33
13	1	8.33
14	1	8.33
Total	12	100.00

Table 1.6
Relevant Kindergarten Seminars or Trainings Attended

Relevant Kindergarten /Seminars or Trainings Attended	Frequency	Percent
a. Kindergarten curriculum guide orientation	10	83.33

b. Developmentally appropriate teaching strategies	7	58.33
c. Play-based learning approaches	9	75.00
d. Classroom assessment and learner progress monitoring	8	66.67
e. Inclusive education and differentiated instruction	7	58.33
f. Classroom management for kindergarten	8	66.67
g. Use of manipulatives and learning materials	8	66.67
h. Child development and early literacy	7	58.33
i. Social-emotional learning in childhood	7	58.33
j. Parent engagement and home-school collaboration	5	41.67
k. others:	0	0.00

Profile for School Heads/Principals

Table 1.7
Sex Distribution of School Heads/Principals

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Female	5	55.60
Male	4	44.40
Total	9	100.00

Table 1.8
Number of Years as School Heads/Principals

Years	Frequency	Percent
5	1	11.10
6	1	11.10
7	1	11.10
9	1	11.10
10	1	11.10
17	2	22.20
21	1	11.10
25	1	11.10
Total	9	100.00

Table 1.9
Highest Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Bachelor's Degree	4	44.4
Master's Degree	3	33.3
Master's Level	2	22.2
Total	9	100.0

Table 1.10
Specialization of School Head/Principals

Specialization	Frequency	Percent
Educational MA	4	44.40
English	1	11.10
General Education	1	11.10
Preschool Education	1	11.10
Social Studies	2	22.20
Total	9	100.00

Table 1.11
Innovations Initiated and Seminars Facilitated

Innovations Initiated in Kindergarten	Frequency	Percent
Implementation of Play-Based Learning Program	6	66.67
Development of Contextualized or Localized Learning Materials	7	77.78
Establishment of Child-Friendly Classroom Environments	8	88.89
Integration of Inclusive Education Practices for Diverse Learners	8	88.89
Strengthening of Parent Involvement Programs	8	88.89
Use of Formative and Developmentally Appropriate Assessment Tools	6	66.67
Integration of ICT or Digital Resources in Kindergarten Instruction	8	88.89
Implementation of School Based-Reading or Numeracy Programs	8	88.89
Establishment of School-Community Partnerships Supporting ECE	5	55.56
Introduction of Health, Nutrition, or Well-Being Programs for Kinder Teachers	7	77.78
OTHERS	1	11.11

Table 1.12
Seminar, Trainings or Workshops Facilitated
or Coordinated

Seminar, Trainings or Workshops Facilitated or Coordinated	Frequency	Percent
Kindergarten Curriculum Implementation	7	77.78
DAP	4	44.44
Play-Based and Experiential Learning	5	55.56
Child Assessment and Documentation in Kindergarten	5	55.56
Inclusive Education and Special Needs in Kindergarten	8	88.89
Classroom Management for Kindergarten Settings	5	55.56
Parent Engagement and Family Involvement in Kindergarten	4	44.44
School-Based Management Related to Kindergarten Programs	6	66.67
Monitoring and Evaluation of Kindergarten Programs	5	55.56
Teacher Professional Development in Kindergarten	6	66.67
Others	0	0.00

Profile for Parents

Table 1.13
Parents' Age Distribution

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percent
20-25	19	14.07
26-30	36	26.67
31-35	34	25.19
36-40	20	14.81
41-45	9	6.67
46-50	9	6.67
51 and above	8	5.93
Total	135	100.00

Table 1.14
Sex Distribution

Sex	Frequency	Percent
FEMALE	120	88.90
MALE	15	11.10
Total	135	100.00

Table 1.15
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
ALS Graduate	1	0.70
ALS/High School	1	0.70
Associate Degree	1	0.70
College Undergraduate	2	1.50
Vocational	2	1.50
College Level	4	3.00
High School Level	9	6.70
Elementary Graduate	13	9.60
Bachelor's Degree	15	11.10
Elementary Level	28	20.70
High School Graduate	59	43.70
Total	135	100.00

Table 1.16
Parents' Occupation

Occupation	Frequency	Percent
Caretaker	1	0.74
Cashier	1	0.74
Driver	1	0.74
Utility Worker	1	0.74
Hotel Staff	1	0.74
Seller	1	0.74
Unemployed	1	0.74
None	1	0.74
BHW	1	0.74

Fisherman	1	0.74
Fish Vendor	1	0.74
Driver/Technician	1	0.74
Lomboy Seller	1	0.74
Sari-Sari Store Seller	1	0.74
Factory Labor	1	0.74
Laborer	1	0.74
Househusband	1	0.70
Pharmacist Assistant	2	1.48
STL Teller	2	1.48
Bus Conductor	2	1.48
Farmer	7	0.74
Housekeeper	11	8.15
Housewife	94	69.63
Total	135	100.00

Perceptions of Teachers in the Extent of Implementation and Teacher Competence

Table 2.1.
Knowledge and Application of Instructional Strategies

A. Knowledge and Application of Instructional Strategies	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. I use developmentally appropriate and child-centered teaching strategies (e.g., <i>hands-on activities, small-group instruction</i>).	3.42	0.79	<i>Excellent</i>
2. I implement instructional strategies that promote the holistic development of learners (e.g., <i>cognitive, social-emotional, physical, and moral development</i>).	3.42	0.79	<i>Excellent</i>
3. I adapt lessons to learners' needs and abilities (e.g., <i>differentiated tasks, varied pacing, or modified materials</i>).	3.58	0.79	<i>Excellent</i>
4. I incorporate play-based and experiential learning in daily instruction (e.g., <i>learning centers, role play, songs, and games</i>).	3.67	0.78	<i>Excellent</i>
5. I reflect on learners' responses and feedback to improve my teaching strategies (e.g., <i>adjusting activities, reteaching concepts, or changing approaches</i>).	3.58	0.67	<i>Excellent</i>
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.53</i>	<i>0.77</i>	<i>Excellent</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 2.2
Use of Assessment Methods

B. Use of Assessment Methods	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. I regularly assess learners using age-appropriate assessment tools (e.g., <i>checklists, observation records</i>).	3.42	0.67	<i>Excellent</i>
2. I use assessment results to guide instruction and interventions (e.g., <i>remediation, enrichment activities</i>).	3.33	0.65	<i>Excellent</i>
3. I document learners' progress using appropriate tools (e.g., <i>checklists, anecdotal records, portfolios</i>).	3.33	0.78	<i>Excellent</i>
4. I provide timely feedback to learners to support their growth (e.g., <i>verbal encouragement, simple corrections, praise</i>).	3.25	0.75	<i>Excellent</i>
5. I consider individual differences in assessment practices to promote inclusive learning (e.g., <i>flexible tasks, varied assessment methods</i>).	3.33	0.78	<i>Excellent</i>
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.33</i>	<i>0.67</i>	<i>Excellent</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 2.3
Integration of Curricular and Co-Curricular Activities

C. Integration of Curricular and Co-Curricular Activities	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. The kindergarten curriculum is implemented in accordance with DepEd guidelines, such as daily routines, play-based learning, and developmentally appropriate activities.	3.67	0.65	<i>Excellent</i>
2. Daily activities address the cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development of learners, such as storytelling, group play, songs, movement activities, and simple problem-solving tasks.	3.58	0.67	<i>Excellent</i>
3. Co-curricular activities support learners' creativity and social skills, such as art activities, music and dance, role-playing, and group games.	3.42	0.67	<i>Excellent</i>
4. Parents and community members participate in co-curricular activities, such as school programs, classroom celebrations, reading sessions, and community events.	3.33	0.49	<i>Excellent</i>
5. Activities are regularly evaluated for their effectiveness in enhancing learner development, such as through teacher observation, learner portfolios, and parent feedback.	3.58	0.67	<i>Excellent</i>
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.52</i>	<i>0.63</i>	<i>Excellent</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 2.4
Utilization of Physical Facilities and Learning Materials

D. Utilization of Physical Facilities and Learning Materials	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. Classroom facilities support effective teaching and learning.	3.33	0.65	<i>Excellent</i>
2. Learning materials that are adequate and appropriate for daily instructional activities.	3.17	0.39	<i>Best</i>
3. Teachers are supported in developing or sourcing additional learning materials.	3.33	0.78	<i>Excellent</i>
4. Classroom organization promotes a safe and child-friendly learning environment.	3.08	0.67	<i>Best</i>
5. Learning materials and resources are regularly updated and accessible to all learners.	3.33	0.78	<i>Excellent</i>
<i>Composite Mean</i>	3.25	0.65	<i>Excellent</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 2.5
Engagement with Parents and Stakeholders

E. Engagement with Parents and Stakeholders	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. Parents are actively engaged in supporting children’s learning.	3.17	0.58	<i>Best</i>
2. Communication with parents is regular and effective.	3.33	0.49	<i>Excellent</i>
3. Collaboration among teachers enhances program implementation.	3.33	0.49	<i>Excellent</i>
4. Stakeholders contribute to school programs, projects, or events.	3.08	0.67	<i>Best</i>
5. Community members participate in initiatives that strengthen the kindergarten program.	3.08	0.67	<i>Best</i>
<i>Composite Mean</i>	3.20	0.58	<i>Best</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Perceptions of Teachers, School Heads/Principals and Parents on the Implementation of Kindergarten Program

Table 3.1
Perceived Availability and Adequacy of Physical Facilities by Teachers

A. Availability and Adequacy of Physical Facilities	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. Classroom facilities support effective teaching and learning	3.25	0.75	<i>Excellent</i>
2. Classroom organization promotes a safe and child-friendly learning environment	3.33	0.78	<i>Excellent</i>

3. Outdoor play areas and facilities are safe and accessible.	2.92	0.79	<i>Best</i>
4. Classroom furniture and fixtures are appropriate for the age and size of learners.	3.08	0.67	<i>Best</i>
5. Safety measures (e.g., emergency protocols, first aid, fencing) are in place and functional.	2.83	0.58	<i>Best</i>
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.08</i>	<i>0.71</i>	<i>Best</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 3.2
Perceived Availability and Adequacy of Physical Facilities by School Heads/Principals

A. Availability and Adequacy of Physical Facilities	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. The school has sufficient classrooms exclusively designated for kindergarten.	3.56	0.53	<i>Excellent</i>
2. Kindergarten classrooms are safe, clean, and child friendly.	3.67	0.50	<i>Excellent</i>
3. Toilets, handwashing facilities, and outdoor play areas meet kindergarten standards.	3.11	0.33	<i>Best</i>
4. Classroom furniture and fixtures are appropriate for the age and size of learners.	3.56	0.53	<i>Excellent</i>
5. Safety measures (e.g., fencing, emergency exits, first-aid facilities) are adequate for kindergarten learners.	3.44	0.53	<i>Excellent</i>
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.47</i>	<i>0.33</i>	<i>Excellent</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 3.3
Perceived Availability and Adequacy of Physical Facilities by Parents

Physical Facilities (<i>Pisikal nga mga Pasilidad</i>)	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. Classrooms are safe, clean, and child friendly. <i>Ang mga lawak-klasehanan luwas, limpyo, ug angay para sa mga bata.</i>	3.61	0.55	<i>Excellent-Labing Maayo</i>
2. There is sufficient space for play and learning activities. <i>Adunay igo nga luna alang sa dula ug mga kalihokan sa pagkat-on.</i>	3.52	0.68	<i>Excellent-Labing Maayo</i>
3. Toilets and handwashing facilities are safe and adequate. <i>Ang mga kasilyas ug handwashing facilities luwas ug saktong lamang.</i>	2.94	0.93	<i>Best-Maayo Kaayo</i>

4. Outdoor play areas are available and well-maintained. <i>Ang mga materyales sa pagkat-on kanunay nga gi-update ug gimintinar.</i>	3.44	0.66	Excellent-Labing Maayo
5. Classroom furniture and equipment are appropriate for children's age and size. (<i>Ang mga muwebles ug gamit sa lawak-klasehanan angay sa edad ug gidak-on sa mga bata.</i>)	3.50	0.67	Excellent-Labing Maayo
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.40</i>	<i>0.70</i>	<i>Maayo</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent–Labing Maayo; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best–Maayo Kaayo; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good–Maayo; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor–Dili Maayo.

Table 3.4
Perceived Availability and Adequacy of Learning Materials by Teachers

B. Availability and Adequacy of Learning Materials	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. Learning materials are adequate and appropriate for daily activities	3.58	0.51	Excellent
2. Teachers are supported in developing or sourcing additional learning materials.	3.42	0.67	Excellent
3. Materials are regularly updated and maintained.	3.42	0.67	Excellent
4. Teachers help children use learning materials effectively.	3.58	0.67	Excellent
5. Materials are developmentally appropriate and aligned with DepEd standards.	3.58	0.51	Excellent
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.52</i>	<i>0.61</i>	<i>Excellent</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 3.5
Perceived Availability and Adequacy of Learning Materials by School Heads/Principals

B. Availability and Adequacy of Learning Materials	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. The school provides adequate learning materials required by the kindergarten curriculum.	3.44	0.53	Excellent
2. Learning materials are developmentally appropriate and aligned with DepEd standards.	3.67	0.50	Excellent
3. Teachers are supported in sourcing, developing, or contextualizing learning materials.	3.44	0.53	Excellent
4. Budget allocation for kindergarten learning materials is sufficient.	3.44	0.53	Excellent

5. Learning materials are regularly updated, maintained, and accessible to both teachers and learners. 3.33 0.50 Excellent

Composite Mean 3.47 0.52 *Excellent*

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 3.6
Perceived Learning Materials-Mga Materyales sa Pagkat-on by Parents

B. Learning Materials-Mga Materyales sa Pagkat-on	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. My child has access to age-appropriate learning materials. <i>Ang akong anak adunay access sa mga materyales sa pagkat-on nga angay sa iyang edad.</i>	3.61	0.64	Excellent-Labing Maayo
2. Toys, manipulatives, and visual aids support my child's learning. <i>Ang mga dulaan, manipulatives, ug visual aids makatabang sa pagkat-on sa akong anak.</i>	3.61	0.66	Excellent-Labing Maayo
3. Art and creative materials are provided by the school. <i>Ang eskwelahan naghatag og art ug creative nga mga materyales.</i>	3.61	0.62	Excellent-Labing Maayo
4. Learning materials are regularly updated and maintained. <i>Ang mga materyales sa pagkat-on kanunay nga gi-update ug gimintinar.</i>	3.67	0.61	Excellent-Labing Maayo
5. Teachers help my child use learning materials effectively. <i>Ang mga magtutudlo motabang sa akong anak sa hustong paggamit sa mga materyales sa pagkat-on.</i>	3.81	0.41	Excellent-Labing Maayo
<i>Composite Mean</i>	3.66	0.59	Excellent-Labing Maayo

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent–Labing Maayo; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best–Maayo Kaayo; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good–Maayo; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor–Dili Maayo.

Table 3.7**Perceived Implementation of Curricular and Co-Curricular Activities by Teachers**

C. Implementation of Curricular and Co-Curricular Activities	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. The curriculum is implemented following DepEd guidelines.	3.58	0.79	Excellent
2. Daily activities address cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development.	3.67	0.49	Excellent
3. Co-curricular activities support children's creativity and social skills.	3.58	0.67	Excellent
4. Parents and community members participate in co-curricular activities.	3.50	0.52	Excellent
5. Activities are regularly evaluated for effectiveness in enhancing learner development.	3.42	0.79	Excellent
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.55</i>	<i>0.65</i>	<i>Excellent</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 3.8**Perceived Implementation of Curricular and Co-Curricular Activities by School head/Principal**

C. Implementation of Curricular and Co-Curricular Activities	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. The kindergarten curriculum is fully implemented and regularly monitored.	3.78	0.44	Excellent
2. Play-based, experiential, and child-centered activities are consistently conducted.	3.67	0.50	Excellent
3. Co-curricular activities enhance learners' social, emotional, and creative development.	3.56	0.53	Excellent
4. Parents and community stakeholders are engaged in school activities.	3.56	0.53	Excellent
5. Daily routines and schedules support holistic child development as prescribed in the kindergarten curriculum guide.	3.78	0.44	Excellent
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.67</i>	<i>0.49</i>	<i>Excellent</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 3.9**Perceived Curricular and Co-Curricular Activities (Kurikular ug Ko-Kurikular nga mga Kalihokan) by Parents**

Curricular and Co-Curricular Activities <i>Kurikular ug Ko-Kurikular nga mga Kalihokan</i>	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. Activities are suitable for my child's age and developmental level. <i>Ang mga kalihokan angay sa edad ug lebel sa paglambo sa akong anak.</i>	3.79	0.47	<i>Excellent-Labing Maayo</i>
2. School programs allow children to express their talents and creativity. <i>Ang mga programa sa eskwelahan nagtugot sa mga bata nga ipakita ang ilang talento ug pagkamamugnaon.</i>	3.76	0.52	<i>Excellent-Labing Maayo</i>
3. Parents are encouraged to participate in school activities. <i>Ang mga ginikanan gidasig sa pag-apil sa mga kalihokan sa eskwelahan.</i>	3.74	0.49	<i>Excellent-Labing Maayo</i>
4. Children are engaged in play-based, experiential, and child-centered activities. <i>Ang mga bata aktibong nalambigit sa play-based, experiential, ug child-centered nga mga kalihokan.</i>	3.74	0.52	<i>Excellent-Labing Maayo</i>
5. School activities promote children's social, emotional, and cognitive development.- <i>Ang mga kalihokan sa eskwelahan nagpalambo sa sosyal, emosyonal, ug kognitibo nga paglambo sa mga bata.</i>	3.81	0.48	<i>Excellent-Labing Maayo</i>
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.77</i>	<i>0.50</i>	<i>Excellent-Labing Maayo</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent–Labing Maayo; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best–Maayo Kaayo; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good–Maayo; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor–Dili Maayo.

Table 3.10**Perceived Effectiveness of Instructional Strategies and Assessment Methods by Teachers**

D. Effectiveness of Instructional Strategies and Assessment Methods	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. I use developmentally appropriate and child-centered teaching strategies.	3.50	0.67	<i>Excellent</i>
2. I regularly assess learners using age-appropriate tools (e.g., <i>checklists, observation records</i>).	3.50	0.67	<i>Excellent</i>
3. I use assessment results to guide instruction and interventions.	3.50	0.67	<i>Excellent</i>
4. I document learners' progress using checklists, observations, or portfolios.	3.50	0.67	<i>Excellent</i>

5. I provide timely feedback to learners to support their growth. 3.33 0.78 *Excellent*

Composite Mean 3.47 0.70 *Excellent*

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 3.11
Perceived Effectiveness of Instructional Strategies and Assessment Methods by School Heads/Principals

D. Effectiveness of Instructional Strategies and Assessment Methods	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. Teachers demonstrate competence in using developmentally appropriate instructional strategies.	3.56	0.53	Excellent
2. Teachers use appropriate assessment tools to monitor learners' progress.	3.67	0.50	Excellent
3. Assessment results are utilized to improve instruction and learning activities.	3.44	0.53	Excellent
4. School monitoring supports effective teaching and assessment practices.	3.33	0.50	Excellent
5. Assessment practices respect individual differences and promote positive learning experiences.	3.44	0.53	Excellent
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.49</i>	<i>0.52</i>	<i>Excellent</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 3.12
Perceived Instructional Practices, Assessment, and Support- Pamaagi sa Pagtudlo, Pagtasa, ug Suporta by Parents

Instructional Practices, Assessment, and Support	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. Teachers are caring and approachable. <i>Ang mga magtutudlo maalagaon ug dali maduol.</i>	3.90	0.31	Excellent-Labing Maayo
2. The school communicates children's progress clearly. <i>Ang eskwelahan klaro nga nagpakigkomunikar mahitungod sa progreso sa mga bata.</i>	3.81	0.47	Excellent-Labing Maayo
3. The school environment is warm and nurturing. <i>Ang palibot sa eskwelahan mainiton ug makapadasig.</i>	3.57	0.66	Excellent-Labing Maayo
4. Parents are encouraged to support children's learning at home. <i>Ang mga ginikanan gidasig sa pagsuporta sa pagkat-on sa mga bata sa balay.</i>	3.82	0.42	Excellent-Labing Maayo

5. Teachers use appropriate methods to understand each child's learning needs. <i>Ang mga magtutudlo naggamit og angay nga mga pamaagi aron masabtan ang tagsa-tagsa ka panginahanglan sa pagkat-on sa bata.</i>	3.87	0.35	Excellent-Labing Maayo
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.79</i>	<i>0.44</i>	<i>Excellent-Labing Maayo</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent–Labing Maayo; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best–Maayo Kaayo; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good–Maayo; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor–Dili Maayo.

Table 3.13
Perceived Stakeholder Support and Positive Practices by Teachers

E. Stakeholder Support and Positive Practices	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. Parents are actively engaged in supporting children's learning.	3.50	0.52	Excellent
2. Collaboration among teachers enhances program implementation.	3.58	0.51	Excellent
3. Stakeholders contribute to school programs, projects, or events.	3.33	0.65	Excellent
4. Community members participate in initiatives that strengthen the kindergarten program.	3.25	0.75	Excellent
5. Teachers are supported and guided in their professional growth.	3.33	0.65	Excellent
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.40</i>	<i>0.62</i>	<i>Excellent</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 3.14
Perceived Stakeholders Support and Positive Practices by School Heads/Principals

E. Stakeholders Support and Positive Practices	Wx	SD	Verbal Description
1. Strong parent–school partnerships support kindergarten learning.	3.44	0.53	Excellent
2. Teachers receive regular supervision, mentoring, and professional support.	3.33	0.50	Excellent
3. Resource mobilization strategies are practiced sustaining the program.	3.44	0.53	Excellent
4. Collaboration with stakeholders strengthens program implementation.	3.33	0.50	Excellent
5. School leadership promotes a supportive and inclusive environment for kindergarten education.	3.56	0.53	Excellent
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>3.42</i>	<i>0.52</i>	<i>Excellent</i>

Note: The following scale was used for interpretation: 4 (3.25–4.00) – Excellent; 3 (2.50–3.24) – Best; 2 (1.75–2.49) – Good; 1 (1.00–1.74) – Poor.

Table 4
Spearman Rho Correlation Between Profile Variables and Level of Competence

Profile Variable	ρ (Spearman's rho)	p-value	Decision
Sex	0.082	.312	Accept H_0
Age	0.221	.009	Reject H_0
Years of Service in Kindergarten	0.195	.018	Reject H_0
Highest Educational Attainment	0.380	.009	Reject H_0
Area of Specialization (Position)	0.143	.152	Accept H_0

Table 5
Kruskal–Wallis Test of Differences in Perceptions Among Respondent Groups

Group	n	Mean Rank
Teachers	135	71.82
School Heads/Principals	9	78.44
Parents	135	70.65

Test Statistic	Value
H	2.63
df	2
p-value	.268
Decision	Accept H_0

Post Hoc Pairwise Comparisons Using Dunn's Test with Bonferroni Correction

Comparison	Mean Rank Difference	p-value	Decision
Teachers vs School Heads	6.62	.402	Accept H_0
Teachers vs Parents	1.17	.781	Accept H_0
School Heads vs Parents	7.79	.365	Accept H_0

Table 6

Analysis of Challenges in the Implementation of the Kindergarten Program (Braun & Clarke, 2006 Framework)

Participant	Verbatim Response	Significant Statement	Initial Code	Focused Code	Theme
P1	“Kulang ug learning materials sa classroom.”	Lack of learning materials	Insufficient materials	Resource limitation	Lack of Instructional Materials
P2	“Daghang bata sa sulod sa room.”	Overcrowded classroom	Large class size	Classroom congestion	Overcrowded Classrooms
P3	“Kulang pagyug ug mga training ang teachers”	Lack of teacher training	Limited training	Professional gap	Limited Teacher Training
P4	“Init ug gamay ang classroom”	Poor classroom condition	Inadequate facilities	Physical constraints	Inadequate Physical Facilities
P5	“Dili tanang parents active sa skwelahan”	Low parental involvement	Lack of parental support	Weak engagement	Limited Parental Support
P6	“Kulang ang gamit para instructional materials ug visual aids.”	Shortage of teaching aids	Lack of resources	Instructional gap	Lack of Instructional Materials
P7	“Lisod mag manage sa bata sa kadaghan”	Difficulty managing large class	Classroom management issue	Overcrowding effect	Overcrowded Classrooms
P8	“Kailangan pa ug mo ug more training”	Need for more training	Need for training	Professional development need	Limited Teacher Training
P9	“Kulang ug ubang gamit ang mga bata”	Lack of equipment	Resource shortage	Material deficiency	Lack of Instructional Materials
P10	“Hindi conducive ang learning environment.”	Poor learning environment	Unfavorable environment	Facility issue	Inadequate Physical Facilities

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study revealed that the Kindergarten Program in selected public elementary schools in Siaton District I was generally implemented effectively across key areas. Results showed that teachers demonstrated a high level of Teacher Competence, particularly in instructional strategies, assessment practices, curricular integration, utilization of learning resources, and stakeholder engagement. These findings indicate that teachers possess the necessary knowledge, pedagogical skills, and professional readiness to provide developmentally appropriate learning experiences for young children. This result is consistent with previous studies which identified teacher quality, instructional competence, and continuous professional development as major factors influencing successful early childhood programs (UNESCO, 2022; OECD, 2021; NAEYC, 2020). It further suggests that teachers' trainings, classroom exposure, and practical experiences contributed positively to their competence and effectiveness in program implementation.

In terms of Program Implementation, respondents positively rated the availability of physical facilities, learning materials, instructional practices, and curricular and co-curricular activities. This implies that schools were generally able to provide the essential components needed to support quality kindergarten learning. The findings support UNICEF (2024), which emphasized that child-friendly environments, sufficient materials, and play-based opportunities are important in promoting children's holistic growth. Similarly, UNESCO (2022) stressed that safe learning spaces and adequate educational resources contribute significantly to school readiness and early achievement. Research also notes that stimulating classroom environments and accessible materials enhance children's motivation, participation, and cognitive growth (Makeleni & Ndu, 2024; Macías Antón & Zambrano Montes, 2024). However, despite favorable ratings, some respondents still noted shortages in resources and inconsistencies in facilities, indicating the need for continued improvement across schools.

For the inferential analysis, the results showed that age, years of service in kindergarten, and highest educational attainment had significant relationships with Teacher Competence. This means that teachers who were older, more experienced, and more academically qualified tended to demonstrate higher levels of competence in implementing the Kindergarten Program. These findings are consistent with studies showing that professional expertise develops through teaching experience, reflective practice, and advanced academic preparation (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020; OECD, 2021; Egert et al., 2020). Experienced teachers are often better able to manage classrooms, adjust instruction, and respond to learner diversity effectively. In contrast, sex and area of specialization were not significantly related to competence, suggesting that effective teaching is influenced more by professional growth and acquired skills than by demographic factors or specialization alone. This indicates the importance of continuous training, mentoring, coaching systems, and opportunities for graduate studies to further enhance teacher capability and sustain instructional quality.

Moreover, the findings revealed no significant difference in the Stakeholder Perceptions of teachers, school heads/principals, and parents regarding the implementation of the Kindergarten Program. Although school heads/principals obtained a slightly higher mean rank than teachers and parents, the differences were not statistically significant. This suggests that the three groups generally shared similar views and common understanding of the present condition of the program. Such consistency may reflect effective communication, collaborative relationships, trust, and shared goals among stakeholders. This finding supports Epstein (2021), who emphasized that strong school-family-community partnerships contribute to more effective educational programs and better learner outcomes. Likewise, Tanque and Brobo, M. A. (2024) noted that active parent-school collaboration strengthens learner development, attendance, and program responsiveness. The alignment of perceptions among respondents therefore indicates a positive climate of cooperation that benefits kindergarten learners.

Despite the positive overall findings, open-ended responses identified several challenges such as limited instructional resources, inconsistent facilities, and the continuing need for professional development. These concerns indicate that while the Kindergarten Program was generally functioning well, sustained support from school leaders, communities, and educational authorities remains necessary. Similar studies found that resource limitations, uneven infrastructure, and insufficient training opportunities remain common barriers in early childhood settings, particularly in rural or under-resourced schools (World Bank, 2022 and Asian Development Bank, 2021). Addressing these concerns is essential to ensure equal access to quality kindergarten education across all schools and communities.

Overall, the findings affirmed that the program was effectively implemented, but continuous improvement efforts are still needed to strengthen quality, consistency, and equity in Kindergarten Education. Schools should continue enhancing facilities, expanding learning materials, investing in teacher development, and sustaining collaborative partnerships among teachers, parents, and administrators. Through these efforts, the Kindergarten Program can become more responsive, inclusive, and capable of providing all learners with a strong foundation for lifelong learning and success (UNESCO, 2022)

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn,

1. The profile of the respondents showed that kindergarten teachers, school heads/principals, and parents possessed varied demographic and professional backgrounds. Teachers generally had appropriate educational qualifications, relevant trainings, and teaching experience. School heads/principals demonstrated varied leadership experience and academic preparation, while parents represented diverse ages, educational attainment, and occupations. These varied backgrounds provided a broad perspective on the status of the Kindergarten Program.

2. Teachers demonstrated a high level of Teacher Competence in implementing the Kindergarten Program, particularly in instructional strategies, assessment methods, curricular integration, utilization of learning resources, and stakeholder engagement. This indicates that teachers were generally capable of delivering developmentally appropriate learning experiences for kindergarten learners.
3. Respondents positively perceived the Program Implementation of the Kindergarten Program in terms of physical facilities, learning materials, curricular and co-curricular activities, instructional practices, and stakeholder support. This suggests that the schools were generally able to provide the necessary conditions for effective kindergarten learning, although some areas still needed enhancement.
4. Significant relationships existed between selected teacher profile variables and Teacher Competence. Specifically, age, years of service in kindergarten, and highest educational attainment were significantly related to competence. This means that professional experience and academic advancement contributed to stronger teaching capability. However, sex and area of specialization were not significantly related to competence.
5. There was no significant difference in the Stakeholder Perceptions of teachers, school heads/principals, and parents regarding the implementation of the Kindergarten Program. This indicates that the three groups shared similar views and common understanding of the current status of the program.
6. Several challenges or gaps were identified in the implementation of the Kindergarten Program, including limited instructional resources, inconsistent facilities, and the continuing need for professional development opportunities for teachers. These issues may affect the consistency and quality of program delivery across schools.
7. Based on the findings, improvement initiatives are necessary to further strengthen the Kindergarten Program. Priority areas include resource enhancement, upgrading of facilities, sustained teacher training, and stronger collaboration among teachers, school heads, parents, and community stakeholders.

Overall, the study concluded that the Kindergarten Program in selected public elementary schools in Siaton District I was generally well implemented, supported by competent teachers and positive stakeholder perceptions, but continuous improvement efforts remain necessary to ensure quality and equitable Kindergarten Education.

Recommendations

1. Strengthen Teacher Professional Development

School administrators and the Department of Education may provide continuous and targeted training programs focusing on early childhood education, child-centered pedagogy, assessment practices, and inclusive education to further enhance teacher competence.

2. Improve Physical Facilities and Learning Environment

Local government units and school stakeholders are encouraged to prioritize the improvement of classrooms, comfort rooms, water supply, and safety measures to ensure a fully safe, child-friendly, and conducive learning environment for kindergarten learners.

3. Enhance Provision of Learning Materials and Resources

Schools should ensure the regular provision, updating, and maintenance of developmentally appropriate learning materials, with possible support from LGUs, NGOs, and community partners to address resource gaps

4. Strengthen Stakeholder Engagement and Collaboration

Schools should intensify partnerships with parents and the community through regular communication, involvement in school activities, and collaborative programs that support children's learning both at home and in school.

5. Improve Monitoring, Supervision, and Feedback Mechanisms

School heads should strengthen instructional supervision, mentoring, and feedback systems to ensure consistent implementation of effective teaching strategies and to support continuous teacher improvement.

6. Promote Inclusive Education and Learner Support Services

Additional support should be provided for learners with special needs through training of teachers, provision of SPED resources, and development of inclusive classroom strategies.

7. Address Learner Welfare Concerns

Schools, in coordination with health and community agencies, should implement programs addressing learner nutrition, safety, and socio-emotional development to support holistic growth.

8. Implement the Proposed Intervention Plan

The Local Government Unit (LGU) of Siaton, in collaboration with DepEd, is encouraged to adopt and implement the proposed intervention plan derived from this study to systematically address identified gaps and strengthen program implementation

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher conducted this study in full adherence to accepted ethical principles and institutional research standards. Prior to data gathering, permission was secured from the appropriate educational authorities and school officials. All participants were properly informed of the nature, purpose, and procedures of the study, and informed consent was obtained before their participation. Respondents were made aware that their participation was entirely voluntary and that they had the right to decline participation or withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or disadvantage.

The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were strictly maintained throughout the conduct of the study. No names or personally identifiable information were disclosed in the questionnaires, analysis, or final report. All information gathered was handled in accordance with applicable Data Privacy principles and was used solely for academic and research purposes. The collected data were treated with care, securely stored, and accessed only by the researcher when necessary.

The well-being, dignity, and rights of the participants were safeguarded at all times. The study involved no physical, psychological, or social harm to the respondents. Questions included in the survey were limited only to information relevant to the objectives of the research. Respect, fairness, and sensitivity were observed during data collection, particularly in guiding respondents who needed clarification.

The researcher further declares that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study. The findings were interpreted objectively and honestly, free from personal bias, favoritism, or manipulation. All sources used in the study were properly acknowledged, and plagiarism was strictly avoided through accurate citation and responsible academic writing.

For full disclosure, artificial intelligence tools were used only to assist in language refinement, organization of ideas, grammar checking, and formatting support. However, all research content, data gathering, analysis, interpretation of findings, conclusions, and recommendations remained the sole responsibility and intellectual work of the researcher.

REFERENCES

- Asian Development Bank. (2021). Early childhood education in Asia and the Pacific. <https://www.adb.org/publications/early-childhood-education-asia-pacific>
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2020). Implications for Educational Practice of the Science of Learning and Development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 24(2), 97–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2018.1537791>
- Department of Education. (2016). Omnibus policy on kindergarten education (DepEd Order No. 47, s. 2016). <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2016/06/17/do-47-s-2016-policy-guidelines-on-the-implementation-of-the-kindergarten-education-program/>
- Egert, F., Dederer, V., & Fukkink, R. G. (2020). The impact of in-service professional development on the quality of teacher-child interactions in early education and care: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 29(100309), 100309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2019.100309>
- Epstein, J.L. (2021) Effects on parents of teachers practices of parent involvement. PsycEXTRA Dataset
- Macías Antón, M. C., & Zambrano Montes, L. C. (2024). Learning environments as enhancers of development. *Journal of the Academy*, 11, 221–242.
- Makeleni, N. T., & Ndu, A. (2024). Inclusive education as a remedy. *Journal of Curriculum and Teaching*, 13(6), 443–452.

- NAEYC. (2020). Developmentally appropriate practice (DAP). <https://www.naeyc.org/resources/position-statements/dap/contents>
- OECD. (2021). *Starting strong VI: Supporting meaningful interactions in early childhood education and care*. <https://www.oecd.org/education/starting-strong-vi-50027004-en.htm>
- Republic Act No. 10157.
(n.d.). https://lawphil.net/statutes/repacts/ra2012/ra_10157_2012.html
- Tanque, Z. H., & Brobo, M. A. (2024). Parents' Participation and Learners' Educational Achievement. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL of MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH and ANALYSIS, 07(10). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmra/v7-i10-35>
- UNESCO. (2022). *Transforming education from within: Current trends in the status and development of teachers*. UNESCO.
- UNICEF. (2020). *Child-friendly schools manual*. <https://www.unicef.org/documents/child-friendly-schools-manual>
- UNICEF. (2024). *The right to a strong foundation: Global report on early childhood care and education*. UNICEF & UNESCO.
- World Bank. (2022). *Investing in early childhood development*. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/earlychildhooddevelopment>